

workflow-1-

September 26, 2024

```
[1]: import geopandas as gpd

# Ruta del archivo shapefile
shapefile_path = ""

# Cargar el shapefile en un GeoDataFrame
gdf = gpd.read_file(shapefile_path)

# Listar las columnas (variables)
print("Variables (columnas) en el shapefile:")
print(gdf.columns)

# Mostrar las primeras líneas de datos
print("\nPrimeras líneas de datos:")
print(gdf.head())
```

Variables (columnas) en el shapefile:

```
Index(['fid', 'OBJECTID', 'BGRI2021', 'DT21', 'DTMN21', 'DTMNR21',
      'DTMNRSEC2', 'SECNUM21', 'SSNUM21', 'SECSSNUM21', 'SUBSECCAO', 'NUTS1',
      'NUTS2', 'NUTS3', 'CLASSICOS', 'C_1-2AL', 'C_3_MAS', 'ERESID', 'E1_2 P',
      'E3_MASP', 'EBEF_1946', 'E1946_1980', 'E1981_2000', 'E2001_2011',
      'E2011_2021', 'E_REPARA', 'AL_TOTAL', 'AL_FAMIL', 'AL_HABIT', 'AL_SEC',
      'R_ACCES', 'R_ESTAC', 'R_PROP', 'R_ARREN', 'ADPTOTAL', 'ADP_1_2',
      'ADP_3_MAS', 'NFAMIL', 'NFPEQUE', 'N_INDIV', 'N_IND_H', 'N_IND_M',
      'IND_0_14', 'IND_15_24', 'IND_25_64', 'IND 65_MAS', 'SHAPE_Leng',
      'SHAPE_Area', 'CO', 'NR', 'O3', 'NH3', 'SO2', 'PM', 'NO2', 'FREGUESIA',
      '_SIN_H', '_1BAS_H', '_ECOMP_H', '_SUP_H', '_SIN_M', '_1BAS_M',
      '_ECOMP_M', '_SUP_M', '_FORA_H', '_SAE_H', '_PRIM_H', '_SEC_H',
      '_TERC_H', '_SAE_M', '_PRIM_M', '_SEC_M', '_TER_M', '_FORA_M', 'km-has',
      '210824_Par', 'geometry'],
      dtype='object')
```

Primeras líneas de datos:

	fid	OBJECTID	BGRI2021	DT21	DTMN21	DTMNR21	DTMNRSEC2	SECNUM21	\
0	1.0	162	16011500143	16	1601	160115	160115001	001	
1	2.0	163	16014600228	16	1601	160146	160146002	002	
2	3.0	164	16010100106	16	1601	160101	160101001	001	
3	4.0	165	16011500144	16	1601	160115	160115001	001	

```
4 5.0      166 16011500145  16  1601  160115 160115001      001
```

```
SSNUM21 SECSSNUM21 ... _SEC_H _TERC_H _SAE_M _PRIM_M _SEC_M _TER_M \
0      43      00143 ...    66     60   335     13     30     79
1      28      00228 ...    10     10   139      3      1     14
2      06      00106 ...    20     25   116      2      8     39
3      44      00144 ...    66     60   335     13     30     79
4      45      00145 ...    66     60   335     13     30     79
```

```
_FORA_M km-has 210824_Par \
0      129  0.059 Cluster 2/7
1       62  0.024 Cluster 7/7
2       39  0.973 Cluster 3/7
3      129  0.050 Cluster 7/7
4      129  0.038 Cluster 7/7
```

```
geometry
0 POLYGON ((-21466.743 250719.011, -20848.162 25...
1 POLYGON ((-8495.261 250691.402, -8413.292 2506...
2 POLYGON ((-26498.776 250777.183, -26495.186 25...
3 POLYGON ((-19673.850 250815.361, -19670.541 25...
4 POLYGON ((-19131.303 250823.636, -19122.721 25...
```

[5 rows x 77 columns]

```
[14]: import geopandas as gpd

# Cargar el shapefile
shapefile_path = ""
gdf = gpd.read_file(shapefile_path)

# Mostrar las primeras filas del GeoDataFrame
print(gdf.head())

# Listar las columnas (incluyendo '210824_Par')
print(gdf.columns)
```

```
fid OBJECTID BGR12021 DT21 DTMN21 DTMNR21 DTMNRSEC2 SECNUM21 \
0 1.0      162 16011500143  16  1601  160115 160115001      001
1 2.0      163 16014600228  16  1601  160146 160146002      002
2 3.0      164 16010100106  16  1601  160101 160101001      001
3 4.0      165 16011500144  16  1601  160115 160115001      001
4 5.0      166 16011500145  16  1601  160115 160115001      001
```

```
SSNUM21 SECSSNUM21 SUBSECCAO NUTS1 NUTS2 NUTS3 CLASSICOS C_1-2AL \
0      43      00143 16011500143     1    11    111         0.0     0.0
1      28      00228 16014600228     1    11    111         8.0     8.0
2      06      00106 16010100106     1    11    111        31.0    31.0
```

3	44	00144	16011500144	1	11	111	3.0	3.0
4	45	00145	16011500145	1	11	111	4.0	4.0

	C_3_MAS	ERESID	E1_2 P	E3_MASP	EBEF_1946	E1946_1980	E1981_2000	\
0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
1	0.0	8.0	8.0	0.0	0.0	4.0	4.0	
2	0.0	31.0	29.0	2.0	7.0	12.0	5.0	
3	0.0	3.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	1.0	
4	0.0	4.0	4.0	0.0	2.0	1.0	1.0	

	E2001_2011	E2011_2021	E_REPARA	AL_TOTAL	AL_FAMIL	AL_HABIT	AL_SEC	\
0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
1	0.0	0.0	0.0	8.0	8.0	3.0	5.0	
2	4.0	3.0	5.0	31.0	31.0	19.0	12.0	
3	0.0	0.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	1.0	2.0	
4	0.0	0.0	2.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	0.0	

	R_ACCES	R_ESTAC	R_PROP	R_ARREN	ADPTOTAL	ADP_1_2	ADP_3_MAS	NFAMIL	\
0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
1	2.0	2.0	3.0	0.0	3.0	3.0	0.0	1.0	
2	6.0	15.0	19.0	0.0	19.0	12.0	7.0	16.0	
3	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	
4	2.0	1.0	4.0	0.0	4.0	1.0	3.0	3.0	

	NFPEQUE	N_INDIV	N_IND_H	N_IND_M	IND_0_14	IND_15_24	IND_25_64	\
0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
1	0.0	4.0	1.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	
2	5.0	47.0	16.0	31.0	2.0	6.0	20.0	
3	0.0	2.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
4	0.0	14.0	8.0	6.0	0.0	0.0	9.0	

	IND 65_MAS	SHAPE_Leng	SHAPE_Area	CD	NR	03	\
0	0.0	7044.078475	135.213073	0.030356	0.444776	0.139334	
1	2.0	17122.676929	601.980255	0.030043	0.380350	0.139331	
2	19.0	1785.277161	15.916914	0.030459	0.515266	0.139369	
3	2.0	9457.158378	349.034014	0.030311	0.444727	0.139248	
4	5.0	11885.045471	348.091537	0.029832	0.410891	0.139169	

	NH3	S02	PM	N02	FREGUESIA	_SIN_H	\
0	1.753877e-09	0.000269	-0.260881	0.000025	Gondoriz	43	
1	1.449464e-09	0.000200	-0.361973	0.000022	Soajo	8	
2	1.753877e-09	0.000269	-0.310539	0.000027	Aboim das Choças	5	
3	1.700037e-09	0.000263	-0.258236	0.000025	Gondoriz	43	
4	1.449464e-09	0.000351	-0.298860	0.000024	Gondoriz	43	

	_1BAS_H	_ECOMP_H	_SUP_H	_SIN_M	_1BAS_M	_ECOMP_M	_SUP_M	_FORA_H	\
0	173	69	19	88	198	61	40	308	
1	76	11	6	27	94	16	5	151	

2	60	19	7	23	62	22	20	101
3	173	69	19	88	198	61	40	308
4	173	69	19	88	198	61	40	308

	_SAE_H	_PRIM_H	_SEC_H	_TERC_H	_SAE_M	_PRIM_M	_SEC_M	_TER_M	_FORA_M	\
0	237	23	66	60	335	13	30	79	129	
1	90	5	10	10	139	3	1	14	62	
2	76	4	20	25	116	2	8	39	39	
3	237	23	66	60	335	13	30	79	129	
4	237	23	66	60	335	13	30	79	129	

```

km-has      210824_Par      geometry
0  0.059 Cluster 2/7 POLYGON ((-21466.743 250719.011, -20848.162 25...
1  0.024 Cluster 7/7 POLYGON ((-8495.261 250691.402, -8413.292 2506...
2  0.973 Cluster 3/7 POLYGON ((-26498.776 250777.183, -26495.186 25...
3  0.050 Cluster 7/7 POLYGON ((-19673.850 250815.361, -19670.541 25...
4  0.038 Cluster 7/7 POLYGON ((-19131.303 250823.636, -19122.721 25...
Index(['fid', 'OBJECTID', 'BGRI2021', 'DT21', 'DTMN21', 'DTMNR21',
      'DTMNRSEC2', 'SECNUM21', 'SSNUM21', 'SECSSNUM21', 'SUBSECCAO', 'NUTS1',
      'NUTS2', 'NUTS3', 'CLASSICOS', 'C_1-2AL', 'C_3_MAS', 'ERESID', 'E1_2 P',
      'E3_MASP', 'EBEF_1946', 'E1946_1980', 'E1981_2000', 'E2001_2011',
      'E2011_2021', 'E_REPARA', 'AL_TOTAL', 'AL_FAMIL', 'AL_HABIT', 'AL_SEC',
      'R_ACCES', 'R_ESTAC', 'R_PROP', 'R_ARREN', 'ADPTOTAL', 'ADP_1_2',
      'ADP_3_MAS', 'NFAMIL', 'NFPEQUE', 'N_INDIV', 'N_IND_H', 'N_IND_M',
      'IND_0_14', 'IND_15_24', 'IND_25_64', 'IND_65_MAS', 'SHAPE_Leng',
      'SHAPE_Area', 'CO', 'NR', 'O3', 'NH3', 'SO2', 'PM', 'NO2', 'FREGUESIA',
      '_SIN_H', '_1BAS_H', '_ECOMP_H', '_SUP_H', '_SIN_M', '_1BAS_M',
      '_ECOMP_M', '_SUP_M', '_FORA_H', '_SAE_H', '_PRIM_H', '_SEC_H',
      '_TERC_H', '_SAE_M', '_PRIM_M', '_SEC_M', '_TER_M', '_FORA_M', 'km-has',
      '210824_Par', 'geometry'],
      dtype='object')

```

This script generates a map to visualize the geographical distribution of seven clusters of ‘emplaced capital footprints’ in Arcos de Valdevez.

```

[6]: import geopandas as gpd
import folium
from folium.features import GeoJsonTooltip

# Cargar el shapefile
shapefile_path = ""
gdf = gpd.read_file(shapefile_path)

# Formatear los valores de NH3, SO2, y NO2 a 6 y 12 decimales
gdf['NH3'] = gdf['NH3'].apply(lambda x: f"{x:.12f}")
gdf['SO2'] = gdf['SO2'].apply(lambda x: f"{x:.6f}")
gdf['NO2'] = gdf['NO2'].apply(lambda x: f"{x:.6f}")

```

```

# Crear un diccionario con los colores para cada cluster
cluster_colors = {
    "Cluster 1/7": '#D73027', # Rojo
    "Cluster 2/7": '#FC8D59', # Naranja oscuro
    "Cluster 3/7": '#FEE08B', # Amarillo
    "Cluster 4/7": '#D9EF8B', # Verde claro
    "Cluster 5/7": '#91CF60', # Verde
    "Cluster 6/7": '#1A9850', # Verde oscuro
    "Cluster 7/7": '#4575B4' # Azul
}

# Asignar colores según el cluster en una nueva columna
gdf['color'] = gdf['210824_Par'].map(cluster_colors)

# Crear un mapa base centrado en el área de interés
m = folium.Map(location=[41.9, -8.3], zoom_start=11, tiles='cartodb positron')

# Añadir el GeoDataFrame como GeoJson al mapa
geojson = folium.GeoJson(
    gdf,
    style_function=lambda feature: {
        'fillColor': feature['properties']['color'],
        'color': 'black',
        'weight': 0.5, # Grosor de los bordes reducido
        'fillOpacity': 0.6,
    },
    tooltip=GeoJsonTooltip(
        fields=["CO", "NR", "O3", "NH3", "SO2", "PM", "NO2", "FREGUESIA", "E1946_1980", "EBEF_1946", "km-has", "210824_Par"],
        aliases=["CO", "NR", "O3", "NH3", "SO2", "PM", "NO2", "Freguesia", "E1946-1980", "EBEF-1946", "Area (km-has)", "Cluster"],
        localize=True
    )
)

# Añadir el GeoJson al mapa
geojson.add_to(m)

# Mostrar el mapa en Jupyter Lab
m

```

[6]: <folium.folium.Map at 0x2de9f0280>

This script generates a dual map to visualize the geographical distribution of seven clusters of ‘emplaced capital footprints’ (in color) and the distribution of the internal freguesias of Arcos de Valdevez (in grayscale).

```

[5]: import geopandas as gpd
import folium
from folium.features import GeoJsonTooltip
from folium.plugins import DualMap
import networkx as nx
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# Cargar el shapefile
shapefile_path = ""
gdf = gpd.read_file(shapefile_path)

# Set font to Times New Roman, size 12
plt.rcParams['font.family'] = 'Times New Roman'
plt.rcParams['font.size'] = 12

# Formatear los valores de NH3, SO2, y NO2 a 6 y 12 decimales
gdf['NH3'] = gdf['NH3'].apply(lambda x: f"{x:.12f}")
gdf['SO2'] = gdf['SO2'].apply(lambda x: f"{x:.6f}")
gdf['NO2'] = gdf['NO2'].apply(lambda x: f"{x:.6f}")

# Crear un grafo basado en las fronteras entre las freguesías
def build_adjacency_graph(gdf):
    G = nx.Graph()
    for i, row in gdf.iterrows():
        G.add_node(row['FREGUESIA'])

    # Añadir aristas entre freguesías adyacentes
    for i, row in gdf.iterrows():
        neighbors = gdf[gdf.geometry.touches(row['geometry'])]['FREGUESIA'].
        ↪tolist()
        for neighbor in neighbors:
            G.add_edge(row['FREGUESIA'], neighbor)
    return G

# Construir el grafo de adyacencia
adjacency_graph = build_adjacency_graph(gdf)

# Colorear el grafo utilizando el algoritmo de coloreado de grafos de networkx
freguesia_colors = nx.coloring.greedy_color(adjacency_graph,
        ↪strategy="largest_first")

# Convertir los colores de números a una escala de grises (valores de 0 a 1)
max_color = max(freguesia_colors.values())
freguesia_colors_gray = {freguesia: f'#{int(255 * (1 - (color_idx /
        ↪max_color))):02x}{int(255 * (1 - (color_idx / max_color))):02x}{int(255 * (1
        ↪- (color_idx / max_color))):02x}'
        for freguesia, color_idx in freguesia_colors.items()}

```

```

# Asignar tonos de gris según la FREGUESIA en una nueva columna
gdf['color_freguesia'] = gdf['FREGUESIA'].map(freguesia_colors_gray)

# Crear un diccionario con los colores para cada cluster (mantenemos los
↳ colores originales para clusters)
cluster_colors = {
    "Cluster 1/7": '#D73027', # Rojo
    "Cluster 2/7": '#FC8D59', # Naranja oscuro
    "Cluster 3/7": '#FEE08B', # Amarillo
    "Cluster 4/7": '#D9EF8B', # Verde claro
    "Cluster 5/7": '#91CF60', # Verde
    "Cluster 6/7": '#1A9850', # Verde oscuro
    "Cluster 7/7": '#4575B4' # Azul
}

# Asignar colores según el cluster en una nueva columna
gdf['color_cluster'] = gdf['210824_Par'].map(cluster_colors)

# Crear un DualMap base centrado en el área de interés
dual_map = DualMap(location=[41.9, -8.3], zoom_start=11, tiles='cartodb_
↳ positron')

# Primer mapa (escala de grises por Freguesia)
geojson_freguesia = folium.GeoJson(
    gdf,
    style_function=lambda feature: {
        'fillColor': feature['properties']['color_freguesia'],
        'color': 'black',
        'weight': 0.3, # Grosor de los bordes reducido
        'fillOpacity': 0.6,
    },
    tooltip=GeoJsonTooltip(
        fields=["CO", "NR", "O3", "NH3", "SO2", "PM", "NO2", "FREGUESIA",
↳ "E1946_1980", "EBEF_1946", "km-has", "210824_Par"],
        aliases=["CO", "NR", "O3", "NH3", "SO2", "PM", "NO2", "Freguesia",
↳ "E1946-1980", "EBEF-1946", "Area (km-has)", "Cluster"],
        localize=True
    )
)

geojson_freguesia.add_to(dual_map.m1)

# Segundo mapa (colores por Cluster)
geojson_cluster = folium.GeoJson(
    gdf,
    style_function=lambda feature: {

```

```

        'fillColor': feature['properties']['color_cluster'],
        'color': 'black',
        'weight': 0.3, # Grosor de los bordes reducido
        'fillOpacity': 0.6,
    },
    tooltip=GeoJsonTooltip(
        fields=["CO", "NR", "O3", "NH3", "SO2", "PM", "NO2", "FREGUESIA",
↪ "E1946_1980", "EBEF_1946", "km-has", "210824_Par"],
        aliases=["CO", "NR", "O3", "NH3", "SO2", "PM", "NO2", "Freguesia",
↪ "E1946-1980", "EBEF-1946", "Area (km-has)", "Cluster"],
        localize=True
    )
)
)

geojson_cluster.add_to(dual_map.m2)

# Mostrar los mapas en Jupyter Lab
dual_map

```

[5]: <folium.plugins.dual_map.DualMap at 0x14fb15060>

This script generates a correlation matrix to visualize the general relationships between active PCA variables.

```

[54]: # Import necessary libraries
import geopandas as gpd
import pandas as pd
import seaborn as sns
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# Load the shapefile
shapefile_path = ""
gdf = gpd.read_file(shapefile_path)

# Set font to Times New Roman, size 12
rcParams['font.family'] = 'Times New Roman'
rcParams['font.size'] = 12

# Select the columns of interest for the correlation analysis, including the
↪ newly converted cluster variable
variables = ["CO", "NR", "O3", "NH3", "SO2", "PM", "NO2", "E1946_1980",
↪ "EBEF_1946", "km-has"]
data = gdf[variables]

# Drop rows with missing values
data_clean = data.dropna()

```

```

# Calculate the correlation matrix
correlation_matrix = data_clean.corr()

# Create a detailed and elegant heatmap for correlation matrix
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 10))

# Use a diverging color palette and set annotations to True for detailed
↳ visualization
sns.heatmap(correlation_matrix, annot=True, cmap='RdBu_r', vmin=-1, vmax=1,
↳ linewidths=0.5, square=True,
            cbar_kws={"shrink": 0.75}, annot_kws={"size": 10})

# Improve layout and add labels
plt.title('Detailed Correlation Matrix', fontsize=16)
plt.xticks(rotation=45, ha='right', fontsize=12)
plt.yticks(rotation=0, fontsize=12)

# Show the plot
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```


This script generates box plots to visualize the distribution of active PCA variables across seven clusters, ensuring consistent y-axis scaling for comparison.

```
[56]: # Import necessary libraries
import geopandas as gpd
import pandas as pd
import seaborn as sns
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# Load the shapefile
shapefile_path = ""
gdf = gpd.read_file(shapefile_path)

# Set font to Times New Roman, size 12
rcParams['font.family'] = 'Times New Roman'
rcParams['font.size'] = 12
```

```

# Convert the cluster variable from string to numeric by extracting the first
↳number (e.g., 'Cluster 1/7' -> 1)
gdf['210824_Par_numeric'] = gdf['210824_Par'].str.extract(r'(\d)').astype(float)

# Create a mapping from numeric to cluster labels
cluster_labels = {1: 'Cluster 1', 2: 'Cluster 2', 3: 'Cluster 3', 4: 'Cluster_
↳4', 5: 'Cluster 5', 6: 'Cluster 6', 7: 'Cluster 7'}

# Apply the mapping to the '210824_Par_numeric' column
gdf['210824_Par_label'] = gdf['210824_Par_numeric'].map(cluster_labels)

# Ensure that the cluster labels are ordered categories
gdf['210824_Par_label'] = pd.Categorical(gdf['210824_Par_label'], categories=[
    'Cluster 1', 'Cluster 2', 'Cluster 3', 'Cluster 4', 'Cluster 5', 'Cluster_
↳6', 'Cluster 7'], ordered=True)

# Select the columns of interest for visualization
variables = ["CO", "NR", "O3", "NH3", "SO2", "PM", "NO2", "E1946_1980",
↳"EBEF_1946", "km-has", "210824_Par_label"]

# Drop rows with missing values for the selected variables
data_clean = gdf[variables].dropna()

# Set up the size of the figure
plt.figure(figsize=(16, 16))

# Create boxplots for each variable by category (210824_Par_label)
for i, var in enumerate(variables[:-1], 1): # Exclude 210824_Par_label
    plt.subplot(4, 3, i)
    sns.boxplot(x='210824_Par_label', y=var, data=data_clean,
↳hue='210824_Par_label', palette="Set3", dodge=False)
    plt.title(f'Distribution of {var} by Cluster')
    plt.xlabel('Cluster')
    plt.ylabel(var)
    plt.xticks(rotation=45)
    plt.legend([], [], frameon=False) # Disable legend

# Adjust the layout
plt.tight_layout()

# Show the plot
plt.show()

```


This script generates violin plots to visualize the distribution of active PCA variables across seven clusters, ensuring consistent y-axis scaling.

0.0.1 LIST OF ACTIVE VARIABLES CONSIDERED (INE-PT, 2024):

- **PM:** Annual Average Concentration of Particulate Matter (2.5 and 10) (year 2023).
- **CO:** Annual Average Concentration of Carbon monoxide (year 2023).
- **NO2:** Annual Average Concentration of Nitrogen dioxide (year 2023).
- **NH3:** Annual Average Concentration of Ammonia (year 2023).
- **O3:** Annual Average Concentration of Ozone (year 2023).
- **SO2:** Annual Average Concentration of Sulfur dioxide (year 2023).
- **EBEF_1946:** Number of buildings constructed before 1946.
- **E1946_1980:** Number of buildings constructed between 1946 and 1980.
- **KM-HAS:** Number of kilometers of roads per hectare (year 2024).

- **NR**: Average Annual Intensity of electric nightlight radiance (year 2022).

```
[53]: # Import necessary libraries
import geopandas as gpd
import pandas as pd
import seaborn as sns
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# Load the shapefile
shapefile_path = ""
gdf = gpd.read_file(shapefile_path)

# Set font to Times New Roman, size 12
rcParams['font.family'] = 'Times New Roman'
rcParams['font.size'] = 12

# Convert the cluster variable from string to numeric by extracting the first
↳number (e.g., 'Cluster 1/7' -> 1)
gdf['210824_Par_numeric'] = gdf['210824_Par'].str.extract(r'(\d)').astype(float)

# Create a mapping from numeric to cluster labels
cluster_labels = {1: 'Cluster 1', 2: 'Cluster 2', 3: 'Cluster 3', 4: 'Cluster
↳4', 5: 'Cluster 5', 6: 'Cluster 6', 7: 'Cluster 7'}

# Apply the mapping to the '210824_Par_numeric' column
gdf['210824_Par_label'] = gdf['210824_Par_numeric'].map(cluster_labels)

# Ensure that the cluster labels are ordered categories
gdf['210824_Par_label'] = pd.Categorical(gdf['210824_Par_label'], categories=[
    'Cluster 1', 'Cluster 2', 'Cluster 3', 'Cluster 4', 'Cluster 5', 'Cluster
↳6', 'Cluster 7'], ordered=True)

# Select the columns of interest for visualization
variables = ["CO", "NR", "O3", "NH3", "SO2", "PM", "NO2", "E1946_1980",
↳"EBEF_1946", "km-has"]

# Drop rows with missing values for the selected variables
data_clean = gdf[variables + ['210824_Par_label']].dropna()

# Find the global min and max for all variables to set a consistent y-axis scale
y_min = data_clean[variables].min().min() # Find the minimum value across all
↳variables
y_max = data_clean[variables].max().max() # Find the maximum value across all
↳variables

# Set up the figure with 4 rows and 4 columns (for 7 clusters)
fig, axes = plt.subplots(4, 2, figsize=(16, 20)) # Adjust figsize as needed
```

```

axes = axes.flatten()

# Plot separate violin plots for each cluster in the grid
for idx, cluster in enumerate(cluster_labels.values()):
    # Filter data for the current cluster
    cluster_data = data_clean[data_clean['210824_Par_label'] == cluster]

    # Create violin plot for each variable in this cluster
    sns.violinplot(data=cluster_data[variables], palette="Set3", inner="box",
↪ax=axes[idx])
    axes[idx].set_title(f'{cluster}')
    axes[idx].set_xticks(range(len(variables)))
    axes[idx].set_xticklabels(variables, rotation=45)

    # Set the y-axis limits to be consistent across all plots
    axes[idx].set_ylim(y_min, y_max)

# Hide the 8th subplot (last one) as we only need 7 clusters
fig.delaxes(axes[-1])

# Adjust layout
plt.tight_layout()

# Show the plot
plt.show()

```


This script generates violin plots to visualize the distribution of supplementary PCA variables across seven clusters, ensuring consistent y-axis scaling.

0.0.2 LIST OF SUPPLEMENTARY VARIABLES CONSIDERED (INE-PT, 2024):

- ****_SUP_H****: Number of individuals with higher education – Men

- ****_SUP_M****: Number of individuals with higher education – Women
- ****_TERC_H****: Number of individuals employed in the tertiary sector – Men
- ****_TERC_M****: Number of individuals employed in the tertiary sector – Women
- ****_ECOMP_H****: Number of individuals with completed education – Men
- ****_ECOMP_M****: Number of individuals with completed education – Women
- ****_SEC_H****: Number of individuals employed in the secondary sector – Men
- ****_SEC_M****: Number of individuals employed in the secondary sector – Women
- ****_FORA_H****: Number of individuals who resided outside the country – Men
- ****_FORA_M****: Number of individuals who resided outside the country – Women
- ****_SIN_H****: Number of individuals with no formal education – Men
- ****_SIN_M****: Number of individuals with no formal education – Women
- ****_SAE_H****: Number of individuals without economic activity – Men
- ****_SAE_M****: Number of individuals without economic activity – Women
- ****_1BAS_H****: Number of individuals with completed 1st cycle education – Men
- ****_1BAS_M****: Number of individuals with completed 1st cycle education – Women
- **R_PROP**: Number of dwellings owned by occupants as usual residence
- **R_ARREN**: Number of dwellings rented as usual residence
- **E1981_2000**: Number of buildings constructed between 1981 and 2000
- **E2001_2011**: Number of buildings constructed between 2001 and 2011
- **E2011_2021**: Number of buildings constructed between 2011 and 2021
- ****_PRIM_M****: Number of individuals employed in the primary sector – Women
- ****_PRIM_H****: Number of individuals employed in the primary sector – Men

```
[51]: # Import necessary libraries
import geopandas as gpd
import pandas as pd
import seaborn as sns
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from matplotlib import rcParams

# Set font to Times New Roman, size 12
rcParams['font.family'] = 'Times New Roman'
rcParams['font.size'] = 12

# Load the shapefile
shapefile_path = ""
gdf = gpd.read_file(shapefile_path)

# Convert the cluster variable from string to numeric by extracting the first
↳ number (e.g., 'Cluster 1/7' -> 1)
gdf['210824_Par_numeric'] = gdf['210824_Par'].str.extract(r'(\d)').astype(float)

# Create a mapping from numeric to cluster labels
cluster_labels = {1: 'Cluster 1', 2: 'Cluster 2', 3: 'Cluster 3', 4: 'Cluster_
↳ 4', 5: 'Cluster 5', 6: 'Cluster 6', 7: 'Cluster 7'}

# Apply the mapping to the '210824_Par_numeric' column
```

```

gdf['210824_Par_label'] = gdf['210824_Par_numeric'].map(cluster_labels)

# Ensure that the cluster labels are ordered categories
gdf['210824_Par_label'] = pd.Categorical(gdf['210824_Par_label'], categories=[
    'Cluster 1', 'Cluster 2', 'Cluster 3', 'Cluster 4', 'Cluster 5', 'Cluster_
↳6', 'Cluster 7'], ordered=True)

# Verificar qué variables están disponibles y ajustar según sea necesario
variables_disponibles = ['_SUP_H', '_SUP_M', '_TERC_H', '_ECOMP_H', '_ECOMP_M',
    '_SEC_H', '_SEC_M', '_FORA_H', '_FORA_M', '_SIN_H',
    '_SIN_M', '_SAE_H', '_SAE_M', '_1BAS_H', '_1BAS_M',
    '_R_PROP', '_R_ARREN', 'E1981_2000', 'E2001_2011',
    'E2011_2021', '_PRIM_M', '_PRIM_H'] # Ajustar_
↳variables

# Drop rows with missing values for the selected variables
data_clean = gdf[variables_disponibles + ['210824_Par_label']].dropna()

# Find the global min and max for all variables to set a consistent y-axis scale
y_min = data_clean[variables_disponibles].min().min() # Find the minimum value_
↳across all variables
y_max = data_clean[variables_disponibles].max().max() # Find the maximum value_
↳across all variables

# Set up the figure with 4 rows and 2 columns (for 7 clusters)
fig, axes = plt.subplots(4, 2, figsize=(16, 20)) # Adjust figsize as needed
axes = axes.flatten()

# Plot separate violin plots for each cluster in the grid
for idx, cluster in enumerate(cluster_labels.values()):
    # Filter data for the current cluster
    cluster_data = data_clean[data_clean['210824_Par_label'] == cluster]

    # Create violin plot for each variable in this cluster
    sns.violinplot(data=cluster_data[variables_disponibles], palette="Set3",_
↳inner="box", ax=axes[idx])
    axes[idx].set_title(f'{cluster}')
    axes[idx].set_xticks(range(len(variables_disponibles)))
    axes[idx].set_xticklabels(variables_disponibles, rotation=90)

    # Set the y-axis limits to be consistent across all plots
    axes[idx].set_ylim(y_min, y_max)

# Hide the 8th subplot (last one) as we only need 7 clusters
fig.delaxes(axes[-1])

# Adjust layout

```

```
plt.tight_layout()
```

```
# Show the plot
```

```
plt.show()
```


[]: